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CDA Organizes its 4th International Conference on Drylands

CDA Hosts Food for West Africa Network Conference

CDA
BAYERO UNIVERSITY
KANO

**CENTRE FOR
DRYLAND AGRICULTURE**
AN AFRICA CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE

CENTRE FOR DRYLAND AGRICULTURE

Bayero University, Kano – Nigeria

... an Africa Centre of Excellence

VISION

Resilient and Prosperous African Drylands

MISSION

To improve livelihood, resilience and sustainable use of natural resources in African drylands through training and demand-driven research

CORE VALUES

- Good leadership and Inclusiveness
- Passion and Teamwork
- Commitment and Sacrifice
- Integrity and Transparency
- Professionalism and Excellence

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CDA Organizes its 4th International Conference on Drylands

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) in collaboration with the International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics (ICRISAT), the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA) and the International Centre for Maize and Wheat Improvement (CIMMYT) organized the 4th International Conference on Drylands with the theme: *Ecosystem Restoration and Natural Resource Management: Exploring Opportunities for Food Security in the Drylands* from 11th to 14th September, 2023.

The conference, which brought together scientists, researchers, agricultural experts and policy makers, represented a convergence of minds, hopes, dreams and aspirations for a better and more sustainable future in the world's dryland environments.

The conference witnessed keynote speeches from experts and scientists from across the world

among whom were Dr Victor R. Squires, an International Dryland Management Consultant, Adelaide, Australia; Professor Rajeev K. Varshney, Director, State Agricultural Biotechnology Centre and Director, Centre for Crop and Food Innovation, International Chairman in Agriculture and Food Security, Food Futures Institute, Murdoch University, Australia and Dr Kevin Vail Pixley, Wheat and Dryland Crops Programs Director at CIMMYT, Mexico.

The theme of the conference aligned with the current United Nations' Decade for Ecosystem Restoration, which underscores the need to restore the planet's fragile ecosystems and food security challenges, said the Director CDA, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, during the opening session.

The Director noted that "Through rigorous training, cutting-edge research, and meaningful outreach, we have strived to enhance the adaptability

of these regions to the ever-changing environmental dynamics.” He said the 4th international conference was a more interesting and enriching experience because it went concurrently with the Food for West Africa network conference.

“In this year’s conference, we proudly introduce an existing collaboration with the Food for West Africa Network (Food4WA), an alliance of Africa Centres of Excellence in agriculture funded by the World Bank and AFD. He explained that the Food4WA’s mission to maximize the collective capabilities of ACEs in West and Central Africa resonates with our commitment to addressing development challenges and enhancing food security through research, training, and community engagement.”

The conference, he said, intended to address the multitude of challenges confronting West and Central Africa relating to low agricultural productivity, climate change and high population pressure through knowledge-sharing platforms.

The Vice-Chancellor, Bayero University, Kano, Professor Sagir Adamu Abbas, described ecosystem restoration as pivotal in shaping research, policies and programs to achieve food security in Africa.

Represented by the Deputy Vice Chancellor, Management Services, Professor Mahmoud Umar Sani, the Vice-Chancellor said the CDA was committed to creating a natural environment that empowers the peasants of dryland to achieve food security.

“It underscores the importance of fostering collaboration and dialogue among scholars, practitioners and policymakers to address the unique challenges of Africa,” he said.

Earlier speaking, the Chairman of the Local Organizing Committee, Professor Aliyu Salisu Barau, emphasized the need for concerted efforts and funds to address the ecological crisis, hunger, food insecurity and extreme poverty and supporting the hard-to-reach populations of the region.

Prof. Barau noted that Africa, most especially West Africa was currently embroiled in vulnerabilities and uncertainties that were unconnected to land degradation and climate change.

Participants observing National Anthem

Chairman of the Local Organizing Committee, Professor Aliyu Salisu Barau

Kevin Vail Pixley, Programs Director, CIMMYT-Mexico presenting keynote address

the 4TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON DRYLANDS

Theme:

Ecosystem Restoration and Natural Resource Management:
Exploring Opportunities for Food Security in the Drylands

Improving climate resilience
Leveraging the success of the Green Economy

Director Centre for Dryland Agriculture,
Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin >>>

DATE:

13-14th September, 2023.

in collaboration with:

IITA

Transforming African Agriculture

AFD
AGENCE FRANÇAISE
DE DÉVELOPPEMENT

In this year's conference, we proudly introduce an existing collaboration with the Food for West Africa Network (Food4WA), an alliance of Africa Centres of Excellence in agriculture funded by the World Bank and AFD. He explained that the Food4WA's mission to maximize the collective capabilities of ACEs in West and Central Africa resonates with our commitment to addressing development challenges and enhancing food security through research, training, and community engagement

me.

Natural Resource Management:
Food Security in the Drylands

CONFERENCE

THEME:

Improving climate-resilient agriculture in W
Leveraging the success of the regional Africa Cent

DATE
11th - 14th September, 2023.
In collaboration

<<< Dr Sylvia Mkandawire,
ACE Project Regional Manager,
AAU

We Must Encourage Innovation, Emerging Technologies to Bolster Agricultural Productivity – Dr Sylvia Mkandawire

Dr Sylvia Mkandawire, the Africa Centre of Excellence (ACE) for Impact Project Regional Manager admitted that it was quite imperative to encourage innovation within the network of ACEs and leverage emerging technologies to bolster agricultural productivity and resilience.

She said our network was a treasure trove of expertise, knowledge and resources. Therefore, fostering continuous collaboration among our participating institutions, industry partners and sectoral policy think tanks as well as expanding our frontiers to other institutions with the aligned vision of honing sustainable agriculture and food security in

Africa was the way to go.

She said by working together, we would tap into resources, share best practices and collectively address the challenges lay ahead.

Speaking at the opening session of the 4th CDA International Conference, Dr Mkandawire noted that, "As we explore the way forward beyond the initial funding of the network, I am aware that productive strides have been taken in this direction already and I would encourage the development of initiatives that have the potential to revolutionize farming practices, improve food security, and empower our communities."

CDA Hosts Food for West Africa Network Conference

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) hosted the Food for West Africa (FOOD4WA) network's first International Conference in Kano.

The Food for West Africa is a network of 7 Agriculture-based Africa centres of excellence, including the Centre of Excellence in Pastoral Productions (CERPP), Universite Abdou Moumouni, Niamey, Niger Republic; Centre of Excellence in Climate Change, Biodiversity and Sustainable Agriculture (CCBAD), Abidjan, Cote D'Ivoire; Centre of Excellence in Food Technology and Research (CEFTER), Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria; Centre of Excellence in Poultry Science (CERSA); University of Lome, Togo; Centre of Excellence in Agriculture for Food and Nutrition Security (CEA-AGRISAN), Universite Cheikh Anta Diop, Senegal and Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA), Bayero University, Kano, Nigeria.

The Vice Chancellor, Professor Sagir Adamu Abbas, who spoke at the opening ceremony on Tuesday, 12th September 2023, said that the theme of the conference encapsulated our collective responsibility as educators, researchers and advocates.

Represented by the Deputy Vice Chancellor, Academics, Professor Sani Muhammad Gumel, the Vice Chancellor said it was his fervent hope that the participants would have the opportunity to engage in stimulating discussions, share groundbreaking research outputs and experiences and explore innovative strategies and interventions aimed at promoting the holistic development of agriculture.

From Left: Director CDA, Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin, Dr Sylvia Mkwandire and Prof Luis Mira da Silva

Professor Koku Tona, CERSA, Togo

DVC Academics, Prof Sani Muhammad Gumel

Dr Baloua Nebie of CIMMYT

Centre Leader of CEFTER, Benue State University, Dr. Barnabas Ikyo introducing members of his team

The Vice Chancellor added that “Your collective goal should not only be to identify the current challenges but also to chart a path forward, one that prioritizes the wellbeing and potential of every African.

The President of Food for West Africa, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, said the network was formed during its consultative assembly held in Lome, Togo in 2021 with the aim of setting up a platform where the 7 ACEs would work in synergy to achieve the objectives of training, research and partnership around food security in sub-Saharan Africa.

The Secretary General of the Food for West Africa Network, Professor Kossi Metowogo, stated that the four key objectives of the network were to establish a network between academics and students from the different ACEs; disseminate the results of research and innovation through conferences and symposia as well as create a digital platform for communication activities.

He explained that members of the network collaborated to seek funding in areas of common interest, citing a partnership between CDA and CCBAD with institutions in Portugal to seek funding from Horizon Europe for a project on Green Energy and climate mitigation.

There were keynote speeches from Dr Baloua Nebie from the International Maize and Wheat Improvement Centre (CIMMYT); Ambassador Rabiou Dagari, Directorate for Technical Cooperation in Africa; Dr Anthony Whitbread, International Livestock Research Institute (ILRI), Professor Jimmy Adegoke, University of Missouri, Kansas City, USA/African Development Bank and Professor Moses Obasi from CEFTER.

Professor Koku Tona of CERSA introducing members of his team

A participant making his contribution during the conference

Group picture of dignitaries and Food for West Africa Network centre leaders

Dr Mkandawire Says Food4WA Network Holds Immense Potential to Drive Agricultural Excellence

The ACE Impact Regional Manager, Dr Sylvia Mkandawire, averred that the Food for West Africa Network held immense potential to drive agricultural excellence across the West and Central African region. She said with its roots firmly planted in the ACE Impact Project. “We have a unique opportunity to not only transform the agricultural landscape but also ensure the sustainability of this network. It is essential that we leverage the successes of the network for its sustainability.”

Dr Mkandawire said this at the Food for West Africa Conference hosted by the Centre for Dryland Agriculture on 12th September,

2023. She commended all 7 centers for the great work and tremendous efforts exerted toward the implementation of this network.

“Permit me to also appreciate the various partners - both industrial and institutional collaborating with this network towards its collective goal of addressing food insecurity in West and Central Africa by increasing agriculture-led economic growth and sustainably improving the key aspects of agricultural research system.

According to her, sustainability demands adaptability. Therefore, the world of agriculture was ever-changing,

with new challenges and opportunities constantly emerging. “Hence, we must remain agile and responsive to these shifts, by adjusting our strategies and research focus as needed to stay relevant and effective,” she said.

Dr Mkandawire added, “We need to strengthen our activities and make the network more vibrant and visible than it is now. In so doing, let's continue to disseminate the results of our research and the innovative solutions we develop. Through effective research communication, we can enhance visibility to attract investment and build a broader support base for the continuity of this network.”

“As we forge ahead, let's remember the prospect we hold as a network. By collaborating, innovating, communicating effectively, and staying adaptable, we can ensure the sustainability of the Food for West Africa Network and continue to make significant strides in transforming agriculture for the betterment of our region.”

Deputy Director Training of CDA, Professor Sanusi Gaya Mohammed (left) and Dr Sylvia Mkandawire (right)

Lack of Consistent Policies Hinder Food Control System, Says Prof. Obasi

The West African sub-region struggles with the lack of consistent policies and standards to guide its food control systems, thereby creating vulnerabilities within the supply chain and the lack of coordination among relevant institutions resulting in ineffective and disunited efforts jeopardizing the region's food security.

This disclosure was made by Professor Moses O. Obasi, of the Centre of Excellence in Food Technology and Research (CEFTER), Benue State University, Makurdi, while presenting a keynote paper on *"The Future of West African Food: Envisioning the Role of Food and Nutrition, Food Safety and Food Deregulation"*, at the Food for West Africa (FOOD4WA) Network Conference themed *"Improving Climate-Resilient Agriculture in West Africa: Leveraging the success of the Regional Africa Centres of Excellence"*.

The conference, which attracted regional and inter-regional scholars of international repute, was hosted by the Centre for Dryland Agriculture between 11th and 14th September, 2023. Prof Obasi added that West Africa's food systems were undergoing a transformation influenced by six key drivers, which

included demographics, economics, sociocultural, policies, environmental and technology.

He indicated that policies, regulations and governance were central to the food systems. To address the present and future challenges involved the expansion of policy levers, the preparation of reasonable food system policies and the integration of different stakeholders from the public, private, and civil society organizations into governance structures.

While presenting the paper, the scholar stressed that the difficulties faced by West African food systems deserved the attention and concerted efforts of researchers. While challenges arose from the absence of enabling policies, inadequate coordination, and imbalances, he was optimistic that such challenges were not insurmountable.

To address this myriad of challenges, the University Don pointed out the urgent need for detailed evaluations of individual countries' food control systems to identify gaps and areas for improvement, allocate resources for technical assistance to enhance the capacity of food control systems and encourage stakeholders' engagement and knowledge sharing to collectively address food system imbalances in the region.

Professor Jimmy Adegoke

Prof Jimmy Adegoke Gives Recipes on Africa's Climate Resilience, Trade and Green Growth Imperatives

Senior Associate of the Africa Development Bank (ADB) and Chairperson, Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) Scientific Industry Advisory Board (SIAB), Professor Jimmy Adegoke, of the University of Missouri's, Kansas City, USA, provided key ways and recipes for future climate resilience, trade, agricultural growth, funding opportunities and sustainable economic development in Africa.

Presenting a keynote address at the 4th CDA International Conference and Food for West Africa Network's conference from 12th to 14th September, 2023 titled: *Agricultural Trade, Green Economy and Climate Finance Opportunities in the West African Food System*, Professor Adegoke spoke on the Africa Continental Free Trade Area (ACFTA) designed to

accelerate intra-African trade and boost Africa's trading position in the global market. He emphasised the need to utilize manufacturing and industrialisation as the silver bullet to fostering trade in the African continent.

He made reference to the intra - African trade of agricultural commodities when he said: "According to the ADB, intra-African trade constituted a meagre 17% of total African export in 2017, compared to Europe's 69%, Asia's 59% and North America's 31%".

The Professor also highlighted the Agric Food Catalytic Financing Mechanism (ACFM) which is purposely made for small and medium-sized enterprises to increase gender equality and build climate resilience in agriculture value chains across Africa. "It offers concessional subordinated debt (up to 35% of total investment facility resources, technical

assistance facility window, grants with a duration of 20 years), including commitment of 5 years,” he added.

Prof. Adegoke suggested that Africa should introduce more circular type systems as an important part of greening the economy. He gave an example of the Africa Development Fund (ADF) cycle 16 climate action window (CAW), an account meant for the most vulnerable countries. He further explained that the CAW focused on climate information and disaster risk, green finance, green infrastructure, water, green energy and agriculture.

“Across the bank, there are several new initiatives focused on the youth especially women entrepreneurs. As a bank we have a very clear mandate to ensure equity and inclusion in all of our programs, everybody keeps talking about the future belonging to the youth but what are we doing about it? what programs do we have in place to ensure that the youth are supported and their capabilities are harnessed and directed towards the development goals

Across the bank, there are several new initiatives focused on the youth especially women entrepreneurs. As a bank we have a very clear mandate to ensure equity and inclusion in all of our programs, everybody keeps talking about the future belonging to the youth but what are we doing about it? what programs do we have in place to ensure that the youth are supported and their capabilities are harnessed and directed towards the development goals and agenda of either the country or the continent?

and agenda of either the country or the continent? The ADB has zeroed in on this as one of the important objectives that should be achieved. One of the key programs the ADB is implementing currently is the triple AP that is, Africa Adaptation Acceleration Program, a 25 billion dollar initiative to accelerate and scale adaptation action in Africa”.

Furthermore, Prof. Adegoke presented the Africa Adaptation Initiative (AAI), an African Union initiative funded by the Global Climate Fund (GCF) in 23 countries in an attempt to simplify the process of accessing loans by small and medium size enterprises aiming to establish more resilient agriculture in Africa.

Professor Jimmy Adegoke applauded the Centre for Dryland Agriculture for its efforts towards improving agriculture in Nigeria and the continent as a whole, saying that the Africa Development Bank was open for coordination and discussion. He stressed that cooperation and teamwork were key to achieving the goals of the CDA.

Cross section of dignitaries at the conference

CDA Organizes Training on Grant Writing and Management

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) has taken a proactive step in advancing capacity building within the University by organizing a comprehensive 5-Day training on Grant Writing and Management. The training, which took place from 3 to 7 July 2023, was aimed at enhancing the capabilities of academic staff from various centres and directorates of the university. The objective was to equip them with the necessary skills to craft compelling proposals that would attract research grants and funding.

The training not only focused on improving the staff's ability to meet the requirements of research proposals domestically and internationally but also aimed at strengthening their overall proficiency in responding to the ever-evolving landscape of grant writing skills, including mapping funders, tracking calls, consortium formation and contracting and research budgeting, as well as overall grants-ship management skills.

The ACE Partner program of the French Institute of Research and Development (IRD) in collaboration with the Centre for Dryland Agriculture facilitated the training.

The Senegalese-based Regional Coordinator of IRD, Dr. Mamadou Aliou Diallo, led the training with invaluable support from esteemed individuals, such as Professor Sanusi Gaya Mohammed and Dr. Murtala Muhammad Badamasi, the Deputy Director, Training and Coordinator, Training at CDA, respectively.

Dr. Diallo emphasized that the primary focus of the training was to expose faculty to the silent issues in

Dr Mamadou Aliou Diallo, Senegalese-based Regional Coordinator of IRD facilitating the training

grant writing and management. He expressed his satisfaction with the participants' positive response and anticipated significant improvement in the grant writing and proposal development ecosystems based on their progress.

During the opening session, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, the Director of CDA, welcomed the participants and encouraged them to seize this opportunity to enhance their proposal writing

skills, which would enable them to create strong proposals capable of securing research grants.

By investing in this capacity-building intervention, the Centre for Dryland Agriculture aims to empower the University staff, enabling them to excel in their research pursuits and secure the necessary funding to drive impactful projects going forward. Participants at training included academics from all the research centres of BUK.

Dr Mamadou Aliou interacting with the participants

A group photograph of WACOT team and CDA team

CDA Enters Agreement with WACOT on Dryland Farming, Sesame Farmers Academy

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA), Bayero University, Kano has entered into agreement with WACOT on sesame farmers academy and dryland farming.

To fast-track the agreement, the Vice Chancellor, Professor Sagir Adamu Abbas, and the representative of WACOT signed a memorandum of understanding to that effect.

WACOT Limited is a member of the TGI Group and a prominent player in Nigeria's agricultural production and crop value chains.

The MoU signed with WACOT seeks to improve dryland farming activities and elevate the WACOT's sesame farmers' academy situated in Gumel, Jigawa State. It also aims to foster a dynamic collaboration through capacity building, curricula development and certification programmes.

Prof Amina Mustapha, the Deputy Director Outreach and Publications of CDA making some demonstrations at Sesame field

The MoU will also facilitate research on sesame improvement and associated technologies, as well as initiatives for afforestation and restoration of indigenous plants and tree species.

The WACOT team had visited the CDA on 19th July, 2023 led by Head of Strategic Partnerships at TGI Group, Habiba Suleiman, and discussed extensively with the CDA team on the areas of collaboration.

The CDA team was led by the Deputy Director Outreach and Publications, Professor Amina Mustapha.

The CDA team also visited WACOT's Sesame Farmers' Academy on 20th July, 2023.

Professor Amina Mustapha said the CDA was thrilled with the partnership as the two institutions were doing things in common. She said WACOT aligned perfectly with the CDA's vision of driving sustained development impact through farmer engagement and private sector collaboration.

The Head of Strategic Partnership of WACOT's TGI Group, Habiba Sulaiman, expressed enthusiasm for the MoU, emphasizing the CDA's expertise in boosting crop and livestock productivity within West and Central Africa's semi-arid and dry sub-humid environments.

Participants listening to the lecture

CDA Conducts 10th Industry Lecture on Academia-Industry Collaboration

Dr P. Soman of JAIN Irrigation, India on 10th July, 2023 presented the 10th Industry Lecture of the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA), which focused on the Industry-Academia collaboration.

Dr Soman explained that both academia and industry needed each other and collaboration between them would be a key to catalyzing innovation and growth in technology and could yield accelerated development of new breakthroughs.

According to him, while the industry often focused on addressing solutions of near-term commercialization, academia, on the other hand focused on building new technology through

research and imparting education to students. He said industry partnerships were instrumental in advancing research and creating a skilled workforce, adding that the industry gained workforce.

Dr Soman noted that the industry gained work-ready talents with specialist knowledge and practical training and the universities benefit by having opportunities to work on relevant technologies and challenging problems.

Using the academia/industry engagement experience of JAIN Irrigation in India, the presenter said the Irrigation firm had a comprehensive collaboration with 27 universities in India, citing many examples, such as a

partnership with MIT Mumbai and Chanakya Foundation in which they worked together to develop a soil moisture sensor enabling predictive irrigation with Jain as a monitor of the project. He said once these sensors were developed, they would enhance precision in the field of irrigation.

Other institutions collaborated with in the area of water and irrigation technology included MIT Jammu, NISER Bhubaneswar, Gayathri Vidyapeeth and Maharashtra.

He said Jain Irrigation had also collaborated with the University of New Mexico State, USA, Swedish University of Agric. Sciences, Umea Plant Science Centre, National Botanical Research Institute, Lucknow, India and

North Maharashtra University in the area of Crop Improvement.

One of the collaborative research projects, according to him was that Jain irrigation realized that the Indian onions were of low TSS (12% and less) and would not be useful for the large dehydration facility built at Jalgaon Headquarters, noting that the buying seeds of high TSS from USA was not a viable option in the long term. As such, they decided to enter into onion breeding to enhance the TSS and be competitive in the market.

He added that Jain recruited a team of scientists in India and worked intensively for 5 years the result which showed a high TSS (15%) variety of white onion and several high TSS breeding lines.

Dr Soman noted that the future of industry-academia collaboration would probably be more and more commonplace since major innovations were hardly ever done in isolation, not even by the largest companies.

He advised that collaborative learning capabilities would be required more often from all the participating institutions, saying that while academic institutions created knowledge, industries look for actionable knowledge items for commercial utilization.

Speaking after the presentation, the Director CDA, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin said this was what was expected of the CDA Industry Lecture to have an enriching lecture that would improve the capacity of PhD and MSc students and open a vista of collaboration between CDA and Jain Irrigation. He said the two institutions would strengthen their collaboration in many other areas, including sending PhD students for internship programmes.

P. Soman presenting the 10th CDA Industry Lecture virtually

While the industry often focused on addressing solutions of near-term commercialization, academia, on the other hand focused on building new technology through research and imparting education to students

The Coordinator Training of CDA, Dr Murtala Muhammad Badamasi, had earlier introduced the speaker, who he said was world renowned agricultural scientist with proficiency and expertise in micro-irrigation, fertigation and precision farming.

The lecture, which was presented via Zoom platform, had in attendance many participants, including faculty members and PhD and MSc students, as well as Dr Bala of JAIN Irrigation from India.

A cross section of the participants

CDA One of Top Performing Centres in Africa – ACE Project Manager

Africa Centers of Excellence Impact Project Team paid a courtesy call to the office of the Vice Chancellor on Tuesday the 12th September, 2023. The visiting team comprised representatives from the World Bank, Association of African Universities (AAU), and National Universities Commission (NUC).

The team leader and Project Manager of Africa Centres of Excellence for Development Impact, Dr. Sylvia Mkandawire of Association of African University (AAU) appreciated the warm reception given to them, saying AAU is subcontracted by the World Bank to support the Africa Centers of Excellence program, with 53 centers in the continent. "There is periodic and mandatory visit scheduled to the institutions to appreciate their efforts and see if there's need to provide direction. It is a check and balance for progress reports on the activities of the centers," she said

Dr Mkandawire said their visit which coincided with the 4th International Conference of the Centre for Dryland Agriculture is a perfect timing and would enable the team more advantage in carrying out its assignment as obligated.

Even though she said, the project as scheduled was nearing its end with 9 months left which is June 2024, but the World Bank is considering an extension till 2025, saying that although it was yet to give an official letter in that respect.

She said this is a huge opportunity for the Centre because the global pandemic of COVID-19 caused some glitches in the implementation process of the program. She commended the Director of the Centre and his team for a job well done, saying although Nigeria started the project late, it was fast enough to catch up among the top 3 performing centres in the region, hoping it exceeds its current position with more success stories to report in the 10th regional workshop in Cote d'Ivoire. She also challenged the Centre to take up on the Disbursement Linked Indicators (DLI) which is of great significance to the World Bank and has been an entry point for them into most institutions.

DVC Academics, Professor Sani Mohammed Gumel (right) presenting souvenirs to Dr Sylvia Mkandawire (middle) while Director CDA, Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin (left) assists

DVC Academics, Professor Sani Mohammed Gumel (right) presenting souvenirs to Prof Luis Mira da Silva (middle) while Director CDA, Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin (left) smiles

DVC Academics, Professor Sani Mohammed Gumel (right) presenting souvenirs to NUC representative (middle) while Director CDA, Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin (left) assists

Dr Sylvia Mkandawire (right) signing visitors' register while Director CDA, Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin watches

In his response, the Vice Chancellor, Professor Sagir Adamu Abbas, who was represented by the DVC (Academics), Professor Sani Muhammad Gumel received the team with excitement, saying "it is with great pleasure to welcome you to this very important mission which is review of

ongoing projects and resource verification, to one of our most important outfits, a center that is key in uplifting the flag of Bayero University Kano higher and higher."The Vice Chancellor expressed the gratitude of the Center and university at large for the World Bank's readiness to extend

the timeline of the ongoing project, which he said is a great news. He also commended the Centre for its foresight and dedication of running two conferences at the same time, saying the university is always ready to give support to the Centre for Dryland Agriculture.

Sudano Sahelian Centre for Sustainable Agriculture Seeks CDA Support

Impressed by the achievement and success stories of the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA), the Sudano-Sahelian Centre for Sustainable Agriculture, Federal University, Dutsinma is seeking the support and assistance of CDA to set up a reputable and sustainable research centre.

The Centre, which was recently established by the Federal University Dutsinma, to bridge the knowledge gap and generate and transmit research knowledge to its host communities, said it was unaware of the trajectory of CDA, which occupied a prominent position among Africa's Centres of Excellence.

A delegation of the centre paid a courtesy visit to CDA to seek support and assistance on 25th July, 2023 led by its pioneer Director, Professor Sanusi Jari. He said the vision of the centre was to be a centre of excellence in research and sustainable agriculture and, to achieve this lofty ambition, the intervention of CDA was paramount.

The centre, according to him, consisted of three

departments of Crop Improvement, Animal and Generic Programmes. He said the Generic Programme dealt with agricultural extension, gender issues, climate change and indigenous knowledge of agriculture production.

Responding, the Director of CDA, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, welcomed the delegation and said that partnership and linkage were some of the activities of the centre under its outreach programmes. He informed them about the activities of the centre and assured them of the CDA's readiness to assist with all that they would require in order to have a successful take-off.

Prof Jibrin added that, as the two centres have many things in common, as such collaboration would be fast tracked.

The two centres have agreed to develop a framework for collaboration and nominate the focal persons from each centre that will lead to signing a formal memorandum of action.

Panel Discussion: Experts Discuss Challenges, Prospects of Agricultural Financing, Small- Holder Farmers and Sustainable Development in West and Central Africa

During the Food for West Africa (FOOD4WA) Network Conference, there was a panel of discussion in which experts drawn from the industry, government, financial institutions, academia and agro-business enterprises that extensively discussed on agricultural financing, value-chain and sustainable agricultural development in the West and Central Africa

The experts included the Senior Consultant, Africa Development Bank (AfDB) and Chairman, CDA International Scientific Advisory Board, Professor Jimmy Adegoke, and the Nigerian Ambassador to Brazil, who is also an expert of Agricultural Financing, Professor Ahmad Muhammad Makarfi,

Others were the Kano branch Manager of Nigerian Agricultural Insurance Cooperation (NAIC), Alhaji Dahiru Abana, Entrepreneur and Agricultural Business Development Service Provider, Alhaji Hassan Hashim, and the Zonal Coordinator (Northwest) of the Nigeria incentive- based risk sharing system for agricultural lending (NIRSAL), Abdulaziz Shehu Galadanci.

The panel was chaired by the former senior special assistant to the former Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development and a former Dean, Dangote Business School, Bayero University Kano, Professor Murtala Sabo Sagagi, who stated that recent evidences suggested that only 5% of small holder farmers had access to credit from the bank and some farmers believed that agriculture was now for the rich.

Alhaji Dahiru Abana, the Kano branch manager of Nigerian Agricultural Insurance Cooperation (NAIC), gave recommendations on how best to improve

access to finance and insurance for agriculture. He said state and local governments should introduce a form of collateral-based lending, so that farmers could know the importance of paying back their loans. Also, there was the need for creating nationwide awareness on the issue of insurance for small holder farmers.

Professor Ahmad Muhammad Makarfi, the Nigerian Ambassador to Brazil when asked to shed more light on the future of mechanisation, said plans were already put in place to have 10,000 tractors and 50,000 farming accessories in every local government with facilities for training. He advised the small-holder farmers to convert extra production to inventories in order to increase access to market and innovation.

From the private sector, Alhaji Hassan Hashim complained that farmers misplaced the purpose of the financial insurance given to them. They took advantage of the money given to them by the government and failed to repay the loans. Speaking about how farmers could get access to finance, Alhaji Hassan stated that the bureaucratic requirements for the financing made it difficult for farmers to access the money due to the issue of illiteracy and lack of understanding. He advocated the need for effective awareness campaign for them to understand the benefit and advantage of insurance and credit facilities.

Alhaji Shehu Galadanci, when discussing about the scope of the Nigeria incentive-based risk sharing system for agricultural lending, explained that farmers with good portfolio had access to loans; farmers who were able to provide credible evidence of their works and had followed the due process of acquiring the loans were better suited for such facilities. He stated

that the challenges in primary production were higher than those in secondary production. These challenges ranged from lack of storage infrastructure, damage incurred during harvest and insufficient fertilizer. He advised that NAIC should make a follow up to farmers after they receive loans.

The Deputy Director (former MD) NIRSAL, Plc Development Finance, Alhaji Sa'ad Hamisu, spoke on the need to transform agriculture from culture to business. He said there was the need to establish a guarantee minute price as well as landmarks, there was a crucial need to carry out soil analysis so as to provide an index of nutrient availability or supply in a given soil. He urged the African Development Bank (AfDB) to set up funds with the CBN so as to increase farmers' access to money.

On his part, the senior special consultant of the African Development Bank (AfDB), Professor Jimmy Adegoke, stated that linking research and development to farmers would bring about profitable and successful agriculture as research was important for growth and development

"The Africa Development Bank has introduced a Feed the Africa Project to transform agriculture into a business framework and drive economic growth by moving the continent towards being a net food exporter," he said.

He further said that Nigerian farmers could benefit from the windows of climate funding from the newly established Agri-Food SME catalytic mechanism (ACFM), a new window that allowed individuals and small medium enterprises to access money, ranging from 25 to 5 million US dollars.

Students from Food4WA Network posing at Tiga Dam

Participants of Food4WA Conference Tour Tiga Dam in Bebeji LGA and Rice Processing Plant at Kura LGA

The Conference of Food for West Africa Network hosted by the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) was concluded with a field tour to a barrage in Tiga Dam, rice fields and rice processing plant. The tour was led by the Director CDA, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, in the

company of other CDA staff. Others were staff of the other ACEs and participants for the conference. The participants first visited the famous Tiga Dam and were carried around the by the staff working at the respective facilities.

The team then visited a rice

processing plant at Kura town of Kura LGA where they conducted a tour around the plant for a visual observation of the facilities with the assistance of the plant manager of operations. From there, the team made a return journey to Kano, thereby concluding the conference activities.

Director CDA and other Food4WA Network teams at Rice Processing Plant in Kura Local Government

Fatima Zahra Buhari, CDA PhD student (1st right), Mrs Fatou Kine Gueye of AGRISAN, Senegal (2nd left) and Susan Ojochide Simon, CDA-PASET PhD Student (left) being presented as the winners of the first, second and third positions respectively in the poster competition at the Food for West Africa Network Conference by the Secretary General of the network, Professor Kossi Metawogo

Fatima Zahra Buhari Wins Poster Competition at Food for West Africa Conference

Fatima Zahra Buhari, a PhD student of Agronomy with specialization in Crops and Cropping Systems in the Drylands at the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) won a poster competition as part of the conference activities for Food for West Africa Network, which took place from 12th to 14th Sept., 2023.

Zahra Buhari and two other contestants that came 2nd and third respectively were presented on the last day of the conference. The Director, Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA), Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, commended the participants of the competition for their resilience and effort in presenting their research work.

During the competition, each of the seven Centres provided one supervisor to supervise the poster competition in which Zahra Buhari emerged as the winner.

Her research focused on sorghum and its anti-nutritional constituents and it sought to address macro-nutrients, malnutrition, feeding and hunger.

Fatima Zahra Buhari (right) making her poster competition

A group photograph of winners of poster presentations and team leaders of Food for West Africa Networks

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